

Microgram determination of ticlopidine hydrochloride in single pharmaceutical preparation by HPLC method

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Abstract : A new HPLC method for the determination of ticlopidine in single and in their pharmaceutical preparations has been described. The method is based on reverse phase liquid chromatography using C-18 column and a suitable mobile phase. The detection is done at 220 nm. The flow rate is adjusted at 1.0 mL/min and the linearity is established.

Keywords : Microgram, HPLC, ticlopidine.

Introduction

Ticlopidine (trade name ticlid) is 3-[(2-chlorophenyl)-methyl]-7-thia-3-azabicyclo[4,3,0]nona-8,10-diene (molecular formula $C_{14}H_{14}NCIS$, molecular weight 263.78). Ticlopidine is an antiplatelet drug in the thienopyridine family like clopidogrel. It is an adenosine diphosphate (ADP) receptor inhibitor. It is used in patients in whom aspirin is not tolerated or in whom dual antiplatelet therapy is desirable.

Literature survey reveals that a few methods are reported¹⁻⁵ for the determination of ticlopidine. Some of these methods involve gas liquid chromatography, capillary gas chromatography and other complicated techniques. The present method describes a simple HPLC method for the determination of the drug in a single pharmaceutical preparation.

Ticlopidine

Results and discussion

The precision of the method was established by carrying out the analysis of analyte ($n = 5$) using the proposed method. The low value of standard deviation shows that the method is precise (Table 1).

Accuracy of the method was checked by recovery studies. Placebo was spiked with known quantities of

standard drug at the level of 80% to 120% of label claim (Table 2).

Table 1. Simultaneous assay of ticlopidine drug

Expt. no.	Assay (as percentage of label claim)
1.	100.50
2.	100.20
3.	99.00
4.	101.00
5.	100.30
Mean	100.20
% RSD	0.736

Table 2. Recovery studies

Sl. no.	Amount added (mg)	Amount found (mg)	Recovery (%)	RSD (%)
1.	4.00	3.99	99.75	0.91
2.	5.00	4.98	99.60	0.69
3.	6.00	6.03	100.05	0.81

Linearity of the method was established by the analysis of standard solution containing 1–5 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for ticlopidine. Specificity of the method was established by injecting the placebo of tablet. No interference of the placebo was observed with the principal peak. Hence the method is specific for this drug.

Ruggedness of the method was determined by carrying out the experiment on different days. It showed that the method was rugged. Robustness of the method was also determined by making slight change in chromatographic condition in buffer pH and temperature. The

modifications did not have any significant effect. The optimum wavelength for the detection was 220 nm at which the detector response was satisfactory for the drug.

The column efficiency was determined from the analyte peaks which are not less than 2000 theoretical plates. The tailing factor for analyte peak is not more than 2.0 and the relative standard deviation for replicate injection is not more than 2.0%. The correlation coefficient, regression equation, linear concentration range and regression coefficient of the method are satisfactory. The above method was validated as per Synder *et al.*⁶ and U.S.P. guideline⁷. The present study shows that the method is fast, selective, precise and reproducible. Hence it can be used for routine quality control analysis.

Experimental

Water, acetonitrile, triethylamine (all HPLC grade), orthophosphoric acid (reagent grade), pump, UV detector, recorder (water 748), injector (Rheodyne fix loop 10 μ L) were used for the experiments. Column (Zorbax XDB C18, 15 cm \times 4.6 mm), temperature 40 $^{\circ}$ C, wavelength fixed at 220 nm and flow rate 1.0 mL/min were maintained throughout the experiment.

Buffer solution : Buffer was prepared by dissolving 2.0 mL of orthophosphoric acid in 1000 mL with milli Q water. The pH was adjusted at 3.0 by triethylamine. The solution was filtered through 0.45 μ m filter.

Mobile phase : Mobile phase was prepared by a mixture of buffer and acetonitrile (85 : 15) and filtered through a membrane by 0.45 μ m porosity. The contents were mixed thoroughly and degassed.

Procedures :

Standard preparation : Accurately weighed 50 mg of ticlopidine hydrochloride (WS) was taken in a 100 mL standard volumetric flask. To this 85 mL of phosphate buffer was added. The solution was shaken well and allowed it to cool at room temperature. 15 mL of acetonitrile was added to a 100 mL standard volumetric flask and mixed properly. 5.0 mL of this solution was transferred to a 50 mL standard volumetric flask and diluted with mobile phase to full volume and mixed properly. A portion of the solution was filtered through a suitable filter of 0.45 μ m porosity and the filtrate was used as standard preparation. An equal volume (10 μ L) of standard preparation was injected into the chromatograph. The recorded chromatogram and the response of the major peaks were measured. The relative retention time was found to be about 0.35 min.

Twenty tablets of the pharmaceutical preparation were weighed and crushed to a fine powdered. Powdered sample equivalent to 100 mg of ticlopidine was weighed and transferred to 100 mL standard volumetric flask. To this about 60 mL of diluent was added and sonicated to 30 min and made the volume upto mark with diluent. It is then shaken well and filtered through 0.45 μ m millipore HVLP filter. The filtrate was collected by discarding few mL of filtrate. 5 ml of this solution was taken in 100 mL volumetric flask and the volume was made upto the mark with diluent. Sample dilution should be approximately equal to standard sample.

The quantity in mg of ticlopidine per average mass of tablet was calculated by using following formula.

Ticlopidine (mg/tablet) =

$$\frac{A_T}{A_s} \times \frac{W_s}{100} \times \frac{5}{50} \times \frac{100}{W_T} \times \frac{100}{5} \times \frac{P}{100} \times \text{Average mass}$$

where, A_T = peak area of sample injections, A_s = peak area of working standard, W_s = weight of working standard taken in mg, W_T = weight of sample taken in mg and P = percentage purity of working standard (on as is basis).

Relative standard deviation (RSD) is calculated by following equation.

$$\text{Standard deviation } (\sigma) = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - x)^2}{n-1}}$$

where, x = average value, x_i = individual value; n = no. of total measurement.

$$\text{Relative standard deviation (RSD) (\%)} = \frac{100\sigma}{x}$$

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